

Method Evaluation Form

This form aims to collect information from each participant about the use of the fitting method.

1. Do you agree that the use of the Adaptation Method helped in the modeling of Context Agents? Justify your answer.
 - a. I totally agree
 - b. partially agree
 - c. undecided
 - d. I partially disagree
 - e. I totally disagree
2. Do you agree that the Adaptation Method allowed the visualization of the reconfiguration process after the context change? Justify your answer.
 - a. I totally agree
 - b. partially agree
 - c. undecided
 - d. I partially disagree
 - e. I totally disagree
3. In your opinion, what was the effort to identify the agents related to the feature model? Justify your answer.
 - a. High
 - b. Medium
 - c. Short
4. In your opinion, what was the effort to model the contexts of each identified agent? Justify your answer.
 - a. \item high
 - b. \medium item
 - c. \item Low
5. Regarding the adaptation simulation process, do you believe that: Justify your answer.
 - a. Helped understand what settings the model will assume from each context change
 - b. It made it difficult to understand, some simulations were confusing or the information was insufficient.

6. What was your main difficulty in using the tool?
7. What are the advantages and disadvantages of the Adaptation Method?
8. What suggestions would you have to improve the Adaptation Method?